

Classical, Classical Statistical and Quantum Mechanical Density of an Oscillator Revisited

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Jan. 8, 2019

In classical mechanics, a spatial density of $dx/v(x)$ can be given even though one particle is involved (1). In statistical mechanics the spatial density is proportional to $\exp(-V(x)/T)$ where $V(x)$ is the potential and T the temperature and in quantum mechanics, it is given by $W(x)W(x)$ for a bound state with a wavefunction $W(x)$. In the case of an oscillator, the high energy eigenvalue density matches that of classical mechanics, while the ground state, that of statistical mechanics. The purpose of this note is to examine how these densities are related to attempt to see why these results hold.

Classical Mechanics

In (1), the density of a classical particle moving in a potential is given by $dt = dx/v(x)$ where $.5mv(x)v(x) + V(x) = E$. A key idea here seems to be that one has one particle and that the one dimensional space is partitioned into equally spaced dx tiny units. Then, even though the speed of the particle entering a particular dx unit differs with x , only one particle is entering - there is no idea of a flux. Once inside the dx unit, the particle may be moving fast or slow depending $v(x)$. If it is moving quickly, the idea is that the density is lower because it is described as being proportional to the time spent in the unit dx . One may argue that this is a somewhat arbitrary way of establishing a density, but such a spatial density matches high energy quantum mechanical spatial densities by the correspondence principle (2) and so seems important.

Classical Statistical Mechanics

In classical statistical mechanics, one has a large number of classical particles. Thus, $1/v(x)$ should be the density for a particle with $v(x)$ at x . One has to be careful as there is both thermal and collective motion in a statistical mechanical gas in a potential. One wants the overall velocity which is a combination of both. Here we consider a one dimensional case. Let us consider a sparse gas which only makes collisions with a wall at temperature T . At first, consider no potential present. The idea of classical statistical mechanics is that one has the same T temperature at each x and a Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution $\exp(-.5mv^2/T)$ for thermal velocity. For a temperature T_1 , one has an average velocity of the order of $\sqrt{T_1}$, while for a second temperature T_2 , $\sqrt{T_2}$. If one takes the idea of spatial density being $1/\text{velocity}$ then it seems that these two cases should have different constant spatial densities. If both systems, however, contain the same number of particles N in the same volume, the density is N/Volume in both. There does not seem to be any link to velocity. It seems that for the case of a gas, one can consider $1/\text{velocity}$ as a spatial density, but one also needs the flux entering the little unit of dx . In the case of one classical particle, there was no such idea of flux. The flux should be

proportional to $N/\text{Volume velocity}$ for no potential and so $N/\text{Volume velocity} * (1/\text{velocity}) = N/\text{Volume}$, the expected density. Thus, velocity drops out of the picture. For the case of a potential, matters are not so simple. In a little region dx , the spatial density is $1/v(x)$, but the flux it seems should be calculated at $x-\delta$, where δ is tiny, so $v(x-\delta)$ should be used. In such a case, one will see changes in density with x . For example, consider a velocity v at x . A particle then moves from x to $x+\delta$ and the velocity changes from v to $v+dv$. Here velocity v includes both thermal (one dimensional) and collective velocity. " dv " occurs strictly from collective motion as there are no collisions in the sparse gas except at the walls of the container. In such a case, if the density is 1 at the place where there is a velocity v , then the spatial density at $x+\delta$ can be written as:

$$\text{Spatial density} = \text{flux} * \text{density in } dx \text{ unit} = v * 1/(v+dv) \approx \text{to first order } 1 - dv/v \quad ((1))$$

$$\text{Now } dp/dt = -dV(x)/dx \text{ and } dx=vdt \text{ so } ((1)) \text{ becomes } 1 - d/dx V(x) (dx/mv*v)$$

For a one dimensional problem on average $mv*v = T$ the temperature and so ((1)) becomes

$\exp(-dV/dx * 1/T)$ which describes the manner in which the density changes for a classical mechanical statistical gas. Thus, it seems that it is the potential giving rise to a collective velocity which causes changes in the density. According to the $1/\text{velocity}$ rule for spatial density, it is actually changes in velocity (i.e. due to collective velocity coming into play) which changes the density.

Quantum Mechanics

In quantum mechanics, the spatial density is given by $W(x)W(x)$ for a bound state where $W(x)$ is the wavefunction. There are two limits, the ground state case and the high energy eigenvalue. one. In both limits, the notion of an average classical velocity appears namely:

$$\text{Kinetic energy average} + V(x) = \text{Energy eigenvalue}$$

$$[\text{Sum over } p \text{ } p^2/2m \int \sin(px)]/W(x) + V(x) = \text{Energy eigenvalue} \quad ((2))$$

High Energy Eigenvalue Case

Even though ((2)) appears as a classical energy conservation equation, it is not clear that one can distinguish a single particle at point x with velocity v at time t . It has been suggested in a number of notes, that a quantum particle may be undergoing zitterbewegung and so the idea of it being at point x at time t does not seem to make sense, even though the particle is moving with an average velocity v . When placed in potential, it has been argued (3), that the particle can scatter from one momentum state to another and that a resonance will occur with cycling between one plane wave momentum state to another given by $\exp(iE_n t)$ where E_n is the energy eigenvalue. For high E_n , the cycling time is very small so that one can distinguish

different time points. Also, high momentum may be involved making Δx small. In such a case, it may be reasonable to think of a single particle with average $v(x)$ at x at t which mimics the classical mechanical case. In such a case, the spatial density from quantum mechanics $W(x)W(x)$ should also mimic $1/v(x)$ which it seems to at least in the case of the oscillator (2).

Low Energy Limit

In the ground state case, things are different. One has many different scattered plane waves and the cycle time can be of the order of the classical time to traverse the entire bound region. Thus, it does not seem that one can recognize a single particle at a point x at time t even though there is an average velocity $v(x)$ at each x given by ((2)). In such a case, one can think of a flux density $W(x) d/dx W(x)$. To see this consider a change in density:

$d/dx[W(x)W(x)] = 2 W(x) dW(x)/dx$ Thus, a change in spatial density from one point to another (for any energy eigenvalue) is related to a flux.

For the case of an oscillator ground state, $W(x)=1/C \exp(-ax^2)$ where C is a normalization constant and a is a constant. Then $W(x)d/dx W(x) = -2ax W(x)W(x)$.

Thus: Spatial density($x+\Delta x$) = Spatial density(x)[1 + $\Delta x (-2ax)$] ((3))

For any energy eigenvalue, one can calculate the average velocity from:

$$.5m v(x)^2 + V(x) = E_n$$

Thus, $m v(x) dv(x)/dx = - dV(x)/dx$. For an oscillator $-dV(x)/dx = -kx$ so:

$dv/dx = -2(k/m)x / v(x)$. From the classical statistical mechanical result ((1)) one has

Spatial density change = $-dV(x)/dx dx / (mv(x) v(x))$ with $mv(x)v(x)$ being set to T , the temperature. Thus, the change is due to $-dV(x)/dx$ or $-kx$. This is of the same form as ((3)) and so both lead to Gaussian results.

It should be noted that in the quantum mechanical case, the flux $W(x) d/dx W(x)$ seems to be an average of fluxes of different plane waves which are "interfering" with each other, thus the microscopic picture is quite complicated. This interference, however, allows for the classical average kinetic energy to be achieved and also for changes in spatial density. In the case of the oscillator ground state, the quantum mechanical flux is mimicking the change in the classical average collective velocity $v(x)$, making both the classical statistical mechanical and the quantum mechanical oscillator ground state look somewhat like fluid flow problems.

Conclusion

In conclusion, choosing a spatial density of $1/v(x)$ for a classical mechanical particle in a potential $V(x)$ seems to be consistent with the statistical mechanical result for spatial density as proportional to $\exp(-V(x)/T)$ if one considers $1/v(x)$ multiplied by a flux proportional to $v(x-\delta)$ where δ is a small number to indicate that the flux is taken a little bit behind the dx interval in which $1/v(x)$ represents the density. For quantum mechanics, one can consider high and low energy limits. In the high energy limit, it is argued that cycling times from $\exp(iEnt)$ i.e. $1/En$, are very low and with high momentum components with small wavelengths, it is almost as if one has a particle at x at t with average velocity $v(x)$, i.e. the classical mechanical case. For the low energy case, the change in spatial density $W(x)W(x)$ is proportional to the flux $W(x)d/dx W(x)$. For the case of a ground state oscillator, this flux is directly related to the change in the collective velocity and so the quantum ground state density and the classical statistical mechanical oscillator density are of the same form.

References

1. Majernick V and Opatiny Y. Entropic uncertainty in classical quantum Oscillator (J Phys A Math Gen, 1995, UK) <http://www.ktf.upol.cz/tom/clanky/jpa96-ent.pdf>
2. <http://hyperphysics.phy-astr.gsu.edu/hbase/quantum/hosc6.html>
3. Ruggeri, Francesco R. The 2x2 Matrix Model and the Schrödinger Equation(preprint, zenodo, 2018)